

SHORT NOTES

Microestimation of Zirconium with P^{32} by Radiometric Procedure

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Successful application of zirconium phosphate as a carrier for palladous iodide and silver iodide in microdetermination of palladium and silver by radiometric procedure¹, thereby overcoming the solubility factor involved in such estimations, led us to find out a suitable carrier in the estimation of zirconium as pyrophosphate with radioactive phosphorus (P^{32}) which is an easily available isotope of convenient half-life.

Carrier-free P^{32} for the purpose was procured from the Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay, as orthophosphoric acid. It was mixed with inactive disodium hydrogen phosphate solution, evaporated to dryness, and the dry mass was heated at 800° for 6 hr. to convert it to $Na_4P_2O_7$ ². A known amount of labelled pyrophosphate solution containing about 2-4 times the theoretical amount as required by the equation:

was mixed with the solution containing Zr. A solution potassium iodide was then added. Zirconium pyrophosphate was coprecipitated along with thalious iodide by adding dropwise thalious sulphate solution. The contents were then centrifuged and a portion of the clear solution was taken by means of a pipette with a filter paper cap at the end. Activity of the solution was measured by means of a liquid counter. From the loss in activity and from a knowledge of pyrophosphate added, zirconium present was computed on the assumption that all the zirconium was carried along with the carrier as the pyrophosphate. pH and other details with certain typical results are recorded in Table I

Table I, column 1 shows that zirconium up to 2 γ can be estimated by the method with a fair degree of accuracy. Errors always lie within statistical fluctuations. It will be further observed that presence of mineral acid exercises some influence as regards the uptake of zirconium pyrophosphate by thalious iodide. Up to 44 γ of zirconium can be estimated in acid medium (pH 0.7), which is advantageous in its estimation in presence of other ions. The table also shows the estimation of zirconium of the order of 90 γ in presence of various foreign ions. It may be possible to estimate zirconium in presence of larger amounts of foreign ions at higher acid concentrations. A study in this line is in progress.

1. Unpublished.

2. Audrieth, "Inorganic Synthesis", Vol III, Mc. Graw-Hill Book Company Inc., 1960, p.103.

TABLE I
Microestimation of zirconium as ZrP_2O_7 .

Zr.	$Na_4P_2O_7$ taken.	Foreign ions.	Tl added as Tl_2SO_4 .	Iodine added	pH.	Zr found.	% Error.
				as KI.			
8.93800 mg.	42.7424 mg.	..	..	..	ca. 0.0	9.1700 mg.	+3.0
1.11700	6.2750	..	..	..	"	1.08000	-2.7
0.56850	2.5100	..	..	..	"	0.56260	+0.7
0.08930	0.5000	..	..	..	ca. 0.70	0.08990	-0.4
0.08930	0.5000	..	50 mg.	40 mg.	"	0.08780	-1.6
0.04460	0.2500	..	"	"	"	0.04210	-6.0
0.04460	0.2500	..	"	"	"	0.04160	-7.0
0.00893	0.0490	..	"	"	2.1-3.4	0.00880	-1.1
0.00893	0.0490	..	"	"	"	0.00900	+1.5
0.00223	0.0258	..	"	"	"	0.00222	-0.4
0.00223	0.0258	..	"	"	"	0.00225	+0.8
0.00111	0.0332	..	"	"	"	0.00138	+18.0
0.00111	0.0332	..	"	"	"	0.00104	-6.0
0.08930	0.4626	Al ³⁺	0.323 mg.	"	ca. 0.7	0.08690	-2.6
0.08930	0.4626		0.647	"	"	0.08510	-4.8
0.08930	0.4626		0.970	"	"	0.08240	-21.0
0.08930	0.4758	Fe ³⁺	0.682	"	"	0.08950	+0.2
0.08930	0.4758		1.764	"	"	0.07850	-12.0
0.08930	0.4758	Fe ²⁺	4.500	"	"	0.08630	-3.3
0.08930	0.4758		6.750	"	"	0.09330	+5.3
0.08930	0.4758		9.100	"	"	0.09950	+11.0
0.08930	0.4758	Ce ³⁺	8.610	"	"	0.09600	+7.0
0.08930	0.4758		17.220	..	"	0.09720	+7.8

N. B. Final volume in each of these cases was made 25 ml. Precipitation was made in a 25-ml volumetric flask at a volume of about 14 to 16 ml.

It is evident from the table that below 50- γ zirconium cannot be estimated at pH 0.7. A higher pH (2.1-3.4) has been found to be convenient for going to still lower concentrations; even 2 γ of zirconium can be estimated with a fair degree of accuracy at the pH range as mentioned.

The method is easy, quick, and much better than the conventional methods. It involves no precipitation, filtration, and ignition. Pyrophosphate is not adsorbed by glass or by the carrier concerned. Studies in detail as regards interfering ions, acidity, and mechanism of uptake will be communicated in future. It may be pointed out that the microestimation of zirconium, using the isotope P^{32} , is feasible under various adverse circumstances where conventional chemical methods fail to solve the problem.

The authors express their thanks to Prof. B. C. Purkayastha for helpful discussions and criticism.